

1-(2-Benzothiazolyl/Benzimidazolyl/Benzoxazolylamino)-4-[(substituted-phenyl)methylene]-2-phenyl-4H-imidazol-5-one

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A number of compounds with benzothiazole, benzimidazole, benzoxazole as parent nuclei are known to possess various biological activities¹. Recently, imidazoles² have also emerged as an important class in the therapy of helminthiasis. These observations prompted us to synthesise the title compounds (Scheme 1) with a view to evaluate their anthelmintic efficacy.

Scheme 1

Compounds of sl. nos. 1, 3, 4, 10 and 11 were screened for their anthelmintic activity against *Hy-menolepis nana* and *Nippostrongylus brasiliensis* in mice. For routine screening against *H. nana* in vivo

the method of Steward³ was followed with slight modification as adopted by Katiyar *et al.*⁴ to suit local conditions. Three newly weaned mice infected with 200 viable ova were used for each sample. Suspensions of the compounds were made with the help of tween-80 and were administered orally at the dose level of 250 mg/kg $\times$ 3, and small intestine was removed and studied. The results were compared with those from control group of animals.

The screening of compounds in vivo against *N. brasiliensis* was carried out in accordance with the method of Whitlock⁵ with slight modifications. Newly weaned male rats were incubated with 500 infected larvae of *N. brasiliensis*. On 9th day, the compounds were administered to rats at a dose of 250 mg/kg $\times$ 3. They were sacrificed next day and the worms in both treated and untreated rats were compared.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) were determined on a Perkin-Elmer 137 spectrophotometer.

2-Benzothiazolyl/Benzimidazolyl/Benzoxazolylhydrazines (1): These were prepared according to a known procedure⁶.

[(4-Substituted-phenyl)methylene]-2-phenyloxazole-5-one (2): These were prepared by the reported procedure⁷.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL* DATA OF COMPOUNDS 3*

Sl. no.	X	R	M p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1.	S	H	115	71	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅ S
2.	S	3-NO ₂	121	82	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅ S
3.	S	4-NO ₂	98	86	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₅ S
4.	S	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	91	77	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₅ S
5.	S	4-OH	141	64	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₅ S
6.	S	2-Cl	107	79	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₅ Cl
7.	S	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	158	82	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₅ S
8.	S	4-OH-3-OCH ₃	92	71	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₅ S
9.	NH	H	102	84	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O
10.	NH	3-NO ₂	136	63	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₅ O
11.	NH	4-NO ₂	132	68	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₅ O
12.	NH	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	96	79	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₅ O
13.	NH	4-OH	>280	81	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₅ O
14.	NH	2-Cl	102	84	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₅ OCl
15.	NH	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	155	64	C ₂₃ H ₂₃ N ₅ O
16.	NH	4-OH-3-OCH ₃	81	75	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₅ O
17.	O	H	111	81	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄
18.	O	3-NO ₂	94	64	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄
19.	O	4-NO ₂	98	79	C ₂₃ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₄
20.	O	3,4-(OCH ₃) ₂	121	65	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄
21.	O	4-OH	184	62	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₄
22.	O	2-Cl	162	71	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₄ Cl
23.	O	4-N(CH ₃) ₂	191	69	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄
24.	O	4-OH-3-OCH ₃	65	65	C ₂₄ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄

ν_{max} compd. sl. no. 2, 1 725 (CO), 3 300 (NH), 1 540 (C=N), 1 315 (C-N), 1 530 (NO₂); sl. no. 13, 1 725 (CO), 3 420 (NH), 1 540 (C=N), 1 315 (C-N), 3 500 (-OH); sl. no. 17, 1 730 (CO), 3 280 (NH), 1 540 (-C=N), 1 315 cm⁻¹ (C-N); δ (CDCl₃) compd. sl. no. 1, 6.0 (1H, s, CH), 7.0-7.8 (14H, m, ArH), 8.2 (1H, bs, NH); sl. no. 14, 6.78 (1H, s, CH), 7.1-7.4 (13H, m, ArH), 9.65 (1H, bs, NH), 10.6 (1H, bs, NH); sl. no. 23, 2.1 (6H, s, 2 $\times$ CH₃), 6.2 (1H, s, CH), 8.5 (1H, bs, NH), 7.2-7.8 (13H, m, ArH).

1-(2-Benzothiazolyl/Benzimidazolyl/Benzoxazolyl-amino)-4-[(substituted-phenyl)methylene]-2-phenyl-4H-imidazol-5-one (3): Equimolar amounts of 2-benzothiazolyl/benzimidazolyl/benzoxazolylhydrazines and [(4-substituted-phenyl)methylene]-2-phenyl-oxazole-5-one were refluxed in pyridine for 4–6 h. The resulting mixture was poured on to the crushed ice containing small amount of HCl (1–2 ml). The solid thus separated was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

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